

Sexual, physical, economic and emotional violence faced by women and adolescent girls living with HIV and at high risk of HIV in South Africa and Nigeria in time of COVID-19.

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Background: The COVID-19 crisis is associated with a global surge in reports of gender-based violence (GBV). Little is known of its impact on adolescent girls and women living with HIV (W&GLHIV) or at high risk of HIV. This study aimed to determine the risk factors for physical, sexual, emotional and economic violence during the COVID-19 crisis.

Methods: National cross-sectional surveys were conducted among W&GLHIV or at high risk of HIV ≥ 15 years in South Africa and Nigeria from July to December 2021. Participants were recruited using a combination of venue-based and snowball convenience sampling methods. The questionnaires were completed online or with assistance from a data collector for those with reading/writing impairment or without an internet-connected device. Multivariable logistic regression was used to identify risk factors for GBV and controlled for age, education and working status.

Results: A third (30%) of the 6,689 participants reported experiencing physical or sexual gender-based violence, with 7% facing less violence, 10% facing the same level of violence and 13% facing more violence than before the COVID-19 crisis. W&GLHIV were more likely (adjusted odds ratio (AOR) 1.27, 95%CI 1.09-1.49) to experience violence compared to those HIV-negative.

There was a monotonic relationship between violence and mental health, with those experiencing violence more than twice likely to report severe symptoms of depression and anxiety (AOR 2.33, 95%CI 1.82-2.99). Violence was also strongly associated with housing insecurity (AOR 1.59, 95%CI 1.27-2.02). Participants engaging in sex work (AOR 2.74, 95%CI 1.62-4.61) or transactional sex (AOR 1.86, 95%CI 1.40-2.46) were more likely to face sexual and physical violence compared to those not engaging in transactional or sex work.

Furthermore, using validated instruments, 35% of all participants reported emotional and economic abuse, with W&GLHIV reporting higher rates of emotional and economic abuse (AOR 1.19, 95%CI 1.04-1.37).

Conclusion: The COVID-19 crisis has increased already high rates of gender-based violence faced by W&GLHIV or at risk of HIV with substantial mental health and economic consequences. COVID-19 and HIV policies and programmes need to pay more attention to the multi-faceted manifestations of GBV.

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